

Proceedings
of the
**Eleventh International Conference on Environmental Management,
Engineering, Planning and Economics (CEMEPE 2024)
and SECOTOX Conference**

Organized by:

- Division of Hydraulics and Environmental Engineering,
Department of Civil Engineering, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki
- Society of Ecotoxicology and Environmental Safety (SECOTOX)

In collaboration with:

- Sector of Industrial Management and Operations Research,
School of Mechanical Engineering, National Technical University of Athens, Greece
- Department of Civil Engineering, University of Thessaly, Greece
- Department of Food Science and Technology, International Hellenic University, Greece
- Department of Environmental Engineering, Democritus University of Thrace, Greece
 - Department of Environmental Studies, University of Thessaly, Greece

Under the aegis of:

School of Civil Engineering, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki

Editors:

A. Kungolos	(chairperson),	Aristotle University of Thessaloniki
C. Laspidou	(vice-chairperson),	University of Thessaly
K. Aravossis	(vice-chairperson),	National Technical University of Athens
P. Samaras	(vice-chairperson),	International Hellenic University
G. Marnellos	(vice-chairperson),	University of Western Macedonia
P. Melidis	(vice-chairperson),	Democritus University of Thrace
G. Papapolymerou	(vice-chairperson),	University of Thessaly
A. Zafeirakou	(vice-chairperson),	Aristotle University of Thessaloniki
C. Emmanouil	(vice-chairperson),	Aristotle University of Thessaloniki
V. Manakou	(vice-chairperson),	Aristotle University of Thessaloniki

June 16-20, 2024 • Lefkada island, Greece

Title:

**Proceedings of the
Eleventh International Conference on Environmental Management,
Engineering, Planning and Economics (CEMEPE 2024)
and SECOTOX Conference**

June 16-20, 2024 • Lefkada island, Greece

ISBN: 978-618-5710-71-2

Copyright © 2024, Grafima Publ.

GRAFIMA PUBLICATIONS

5, Eksadaktylou str., 546 35 Thessaloniki, Greece

Tel./Fax: 2310.248272, e-mail: grafima@grafima.com.gr

www.grafima.com.gr ΕΚΔΟΣΕΙΣ ΓΡΑΦΗΜΑ

Organizing and Scientific Board

Kungolos A., (chairperson) Aristotle University of Thessaloniki
Laspidou C., (vice-chairperson) University of Thessaly
Aravossis K., (vice-chairperson) National Technical University of Athens
Samaras P., (vice-chairperson) International Hellenic University
Marnellos G., (vice-chairperson) University of Western Macedonia
Melidis P., (vice-chairperson) Democritus University of Thrace
Papapolymerou G., (vice-chairperson) University of Thessaly
Zafirakou A., (vice-chairperson) Aristotle University of Thessaloniki
Tsiakis T., International Hellenic University
Emmanouil C., Aristotle University of Thessaloniki
Giannakis I., Aristotle University of Thessaloniki
Manakou V., Aristotle University of Thessaloniki
Mimis S., University of Thessaly
Ntailiani P., Aristotle University of Thessaloniki
Papaoikonomou K., University of Thessaly
Poulios K., Aristotle University of Thessaloniki
Tryfona-Panagopoulou V., Aristotle University of Thessaloniki

International Scientific Committee

(All members of the organizing committee plus the following scientists)

Abdalla F.C., Federal University of São Carlos (Brazil)
Abeliotis K., Harokopio University (Greece)
Adamos G., Aristotle University of Thessaloniki (Greece)
Aretoulis G., Aristotle University of Thessaloniki (Greece)
Arsenos P., University of West Attica (Greece)
Baltas E., National Technical University of Athens (Greece)
Bareka P., Agricultural University of Athens (Greece)
Constantin C., University Politehnica of Bucharest (Romania)
Crispim A., ISEP (Portugal)
Dagiliūtė R., Vytautas Magnus University (Lithuania)
Dailianis S., University of Patras (Greece)
Diamantis V., Democritus University of Thrace (Greece)
Diapouli E., NCSR Demokritos (Greece)
Di Nardo A., Second University of Naples (Italy)
Dogan Saglamtimur N., University of Nigde (Turkey)
Eleftheriadis K., NCSR Demokritos (Greece)
Frank H., University of Bayreuth (Germany)
Gagné F., Environment and Climate Change Canada (Canada)
Gaidajis G., Democritus University of Thrace (Greece)
Gikas P., Technical University of Crete (Greece)
Golia E., Aristotle University of Thessaloniki (Greece)
Ioannou A., University of Thessaly (Greece)
Kalavrouziotis I., Hellenic Open University (Greece)
Kamari G., University of Patras (Greece)
Kampioti A., Ionian University (Greece)
Kanakoudis V., Aristotle University of Thessaloniki (Greece)
Karakitsios S., Aristotle University of Thessaloniki (Greece)

Karampas T., Aristotle University of Thessaloniki (Greece)
Karanis P., University of Nicosia Medical School (Cyprus)
Karayiannis V., University of Western Macedonia (Greece)
Kasiteropoulou D., University of Thessaly (Greece)
Katakalos K., Aristotle University of Thessaloniki (Greece)
Katsou E., Brunel University London (United Kingdom)
Kehagia F., Aristotle University of Thessaloniki (Greece)
Kofinas D., University of Thessaly (Greece)
Kyzas G., International Hellenic University (Greece)
Lasaridi K., Harokopio University (Greece)
Latinopoulos D., Aristotle University of Thessaloniki (Greece)
Malamis S., National Technical University of Athens (Greece)
Mallios Z., Aristotle University of Thessaloniki (Greece)
Mantzavinos D., University of Patras (Greece)
Manusadzianas L., Institute of Botany (Lithuania)
Markov Z., "Ss. Cyril and Methodius" University (FYROM)
Marmanis D., International Hellenic University (Greece)
Mellios N., University of Thessaly (Greece)
Minier C., University of Le Havre (France)
Moussiopoulos N., Aristotle University of Thessaloniki (Greece)
Muhammetoglu H., Akdeniz University (Turkey)
Muhammetoglu A., Akdeniz University (Turkey)
Ntaikou I., University of Patras (Greece)
Ntougias S., Democritus University of Thrace (Greece)
Okamura H., Kobe University (Japan)
Panagiotaras D., Ionian University (Greece)
Papadaki M., University of Patras (Greece)
Papadimitriou C., Agricultural University of Athens (Greece)
Papadopoulou M., National Technical University of Athens (Greece)
Papanastasiou D., University of Thessaly (Greece)
Pirozzi F., The University of Naples Federico II (Italy)
Psomopoulos K., University of West Attica (Greece)
Romanowska-Duda Z., University of Lodz (Poland)
Sarigiannis D., Aristotle University of Thessaloniki (Greece)
Sarioglu M., Cumhuriyet University (Turkey)
Skrbic B., University of Novi Sad (Republic of Serbia)
Spiliotis X., University of Thessaly (Greece)
Spyropoulou A., University of Thessaly (Greece)
Stamou A., National Technical University of Athens (Greece)
Stergiadou A., Aristotle University of Thessaloniki (Greece)
Sylaios G., Democritus University of Thrace (Greece)
Theodosiou N., Aristotle University of Thessaloniki (Greece)
Thoidou E., Aristotle University of Thessaloniki (Greece)
Tsakiroglou C., FORTH/ICE-HT (Greece)
Tsihrintzis V., National Technical University of Athens (Greece)
Tsitsoni T., Aristotle University of Thessaloniki (Greece)
Tuneski A., "Ss. Cyril and Methodius" University (North Macedonia)
Vagiona D., Aristotle University of Thessaloniki (Greece)
Zeng Q., Chengdu University of Technology (China)
Zorpas A., Open University of Cyprus (Cyprus)

Editors' Preface

The 11th CEMEPE Conference deals with environmental engineering and management, incorporating subject areas related to planning and economics, aiming at creating a potential for osmosis between environmentalists and other scientists such as economists, engineers, planners, policy makers etc. The conference is designed to encourage the exchange of ideas and knowledge between diverse groups of the scientific community concerned by current issues in environmental science, engineering, management, planning and economics. The 1st, 3rd and 10th CEMEPE conferences were successfully completed in the picturesque Skiathos island in June 2007, 2011 and 2023 respectively; the 2nd, 4th, 5th, 7th and 9th were held in the famous island of Mykonos in 2009, 2013, 2015, 2019 and 2022 the 6th and 8th took place in the city of Thessaloniki in June 2017 and in July 2021 respectively. The current 11th CEMEPE takes place in Lefkada island, Greece. A total of 152 manuscripts are included in the conference proceedings. Participants from more than 20 countries contributed their work to the conference. A book of proceedings including all the participations was edited and published as e-proceedings in a CD-ROM complete with ISBN number. Participations have been classified in the following topics:

- Energy and environment (16)
- Advances in wastewater management (6)
- Environmental impact assessment and risk analysis (14)
- Air quality and health (20)
- Global climate change (7)
- Ecotoxicology and environmental toxicology (20)
- Natural resources management (11)
- NexusNet-COST action network on Water-Energy-Food Nexus (7)
- Advances in water and wastewater treatment (14)
- Industrial symbiosis and sustainable production (21)
- Environmental education (7)
- Environmental economics (5)
- Environmental legislation and policies (4)

The editors would like to thank and acknowledge the aid of the following:

- The SECOTOX Society for being eager to organize a joint event with CEMEPE;
- The participating authors for their scientific contribution;
- The reviewers of the participating submissions for their invaluable help;
- The sponsors of the 11th CEMEPE Conference for their financial support, which has enabled keeping the fees at a reasonable cost;
- All participants for their involvement in the exchange of knowledge, know-how and ideas, which is the essence of this conference;
- Grafima Publications for their collaboration as well as for their contribution to the editing of both the book of abstracts and the e-proceedings.

Athanassios Kungolos
Chrysi Laspidou
Konstantinos Aravossis
Petros Samaras
Georgios Marnellos
Paraschos Melidis
Georgios Papapolymerou
Antigoni Zafeirakou
Christina Emmanouil
Vicky Manakou

Table of Contents

Organizing and Scientific Board	<i>iii</i>
International Scientific Committee	<i>iii</i>
Editor’s Preface	<i>v</i>
Conference Program	<i>vii</i>

Energy and Environment

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Optimization of e-methane Production with the Use of Photovoltaic Power Plants <i>S. Efstratiou, D. G. Vagiona</i>..... 	<i>3</i>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● A Panhellenic Research (2024) Regarding the Attitudes Towards Energy, Renewable Energy Sources, Economy, and the Climatic Crisis <i>P. Kosmopoulos, K. Kleskas</i>..... 	<i>13</i>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Alternative Fuels for Marine Transportation: do Cryogenics Offer a Solution Concerning Environmental Protection? <i>Z. Nivolianitou</i>..... 	<i>26</i>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● The Clustering in the OFFSHORE Energy Sector. A European and an Asian Perspective <i>A. Pego</i> 	<i>27</i>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Synthesis of Ni/LaAlO₃ – Perovskite Catalysts via a MOF Precursor for the Dry Reforming of Methane <i>H.J. Muñoz, A. Gil, S.A. Korili</i>..... 	<i>28</i>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Development of a Hybrid Renewable Energy System to Cover the Water and Energy Demand on the Island of Kefalonia <i>G.Pasaniotis, A.-F. Papathanasiou, E. Baltas</i> 	<i>29</i>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Multi-Criteria Site Selection for a Wind Park in Karpathos Island using Geographical Information Systems <i>M.M. Bertsiou, A.P. Theochari, E. Baltas</i> 	<i>38</i>

- **Lemnaceae Plants Superheated Steam Torrefaction Process and its Conditions Effects on Phytotoxicity**
Z. Romanowska-Duda, S. Szufa, H. Unyay, C. Emmanouil, A. Kungolos..... 39
- **Hydrogen-Rich Syngas from Co-Gasification of Forest Residues with Lignite under a Steam Atmosphere**
D. Vamvuka, K. Zacheila, S. Panagiotidou, A. Orfanoudaki..... 40
- **Evaluation of Biogas Recovery Potential from Livestock Wastes and Techno-Economic Assessment of Small-Scale Biogas Production Facilities**
A. Eftaxias, C. Michailidis, I. Kolokotroni, D. Marmanis, V. Diamantis..... 41
- **The Role of Co-Opetition within the Context of Environmental Sustainability: A System dynamics based Causal Loop Diagram (CLD) Approach**
A. K. Konyaltoğlu, A. Ates, S. Paton..... 42
- **Investigation of Management of Water and Energy Needs in the Stratos Reservoir Using RES**
K. S. Spiropoulou, S. Skroufouta, E. Baltas..... 50
- **Choice of the Filter for Tar Removal from Syngas**
S. Osipovs and A. Pučkins..... 62
- **Impacts of Conservation and Precision Agriculture Management Practices on Energy Use and Carbon Footprint of Winter Cereals**
C. Cavalaris, V. Giouvanis, C. Karamoutis, M. Moraitis, M. Kosti, A. Zamidis, H. Lampropoulos, A. Balafoutis..... 63
- **Comparative Impact Assessment of Photovoltaic Technologies via Life Cycle Analysis**
A. Menti, N. Skarkos, I. Chronis, K. Kalkanis, C. S. Psomopoulos..... 66
- **Performance Assessment of Biotrickling Filters for Biogas Upgrade to Biomethane: Effect of Packing Material Type and Gas Retention Time**
C. Karyofyllidou, A. Spyridonidis, V. Diamantis, K. Stamatelatou..... 67

Advances in Wastewater Management

- **Synthesis of Layered Double Hydroxides from an Industrial Waste for CO₂ Adsorption at Moderate Temperatures**
A. Gil, L. Santamaria, S.A. Korili..... 71
- **Microplastics Monitoring of Midlittoral and Supralittoral Areas in Northern Part of Thermaikos Gulf, NW Aegean Sea**
C.A. Papadimitriou, S.Apostolides, F.Vaggeli, S. Galinou-Mitsoudi..... 72

- **Removal of Zinc by Side Stream-Based Alkali-Activated Material – Optimization of Prewashing and its Effect to Adsorption and Regeneration**
M. Korhonen, P. Dahl, H. Runtti, T. Kangas, A. Heponiemi, T. Hu, U. Lassi, S. Tuomikoski 83
- **Biobleaching of Critical Raw Materials from Hungarian Bauxite Residue**
V. Feigl, D. Mukics, B. Vankó, Zs. Janek, J. Dorogi..... 84
- **Utilization of Municipal Food Wastes for the Production of Livestock Feed**
I. Langousi, C. Eliopoulos, E. Kougia, G. Markou, D. Arapoglou..... 85
- **Single-Use Food Plastic Packaging in Greek Supermarkets: Current Data and Alternatives**
N. Moutsaki, G. Palantzas, A. Zafeirakou 86

Environmental Impact Assessment and Risk Analysis

- **Temporal Transformations of Trace Element Binding in Sewage Sludge in View of Environmental Safety of Amended Agricultural Lands**
E. Miszczak, S. Stefaniak, I. Twardowska..... 89
- **Evaluating Coastal Inundation in a Climate Change Scenario: the Case of the Marche Region**
A. Baldoni, F. Marini, L. Melito, C. Lorenzoni, M. Brocchini..... 91
- **Assessing and Mitigating the Environmental Impact of Warfare on Ukraine’s Aquatic Ecosystems: a Comprehensive Approach to Restoration**
D. Montvydienė, J. Karosienė, N. Kazlauskienė, S. N. Matviienko, Skrotskyi, Ž. Jurgelėnė 93
- **Influence of Water Physicochemical Properties on Radon Concentration**
C. Trull Hernandis, A. Noverques Medina, B. Juste Vidal, M. Sancho Fernández, G. Verdú Martín 94
- **Radioactive Characterization of Spanish Soils Contaminated with Phosphoric Acid Byproducts**
C. Trull Hernandis, A. Noverques Medina, C. Pereira Ricardo, B. Juste Vidal, M. Sancho Fernández, G. Verdú Martín, A. Heeren de Oliveira, C. Pereira Bezerra Lima 95
- **Coastal Engineering Studies and Serious Erosion Phenomena along the SSW Coast of Piraeus, Greece**
B.S. Tselentis, G. Gkimtsas, K. Mavrilakos, D.Vini..... 96
- **Spatial Distribution of Heavy Metals Co, Cr, Mn and Ni in the Urban Area of Thessaloniki**
O.D. Kantzou, E.E. Golia, T.K. Alexandridis, N. Barbayiannis..... 97

- **Microbiological Assessment of Ecological Condition of Selected Water Bodies in the Kakhovka Disaster Zone**
L. Khomenko, O. Vasyliuk, S. Skrotskyi..... 98
- **Classification of Post-Fire Soil Contamination by Heavy Metals (Cr, Ni, Pb, Zn) in Wildfire Affected Areas in Greece, using Laser Induced Breakdown Spectroscopy and Machine Learning**
G. Kantemiris, E. Xenogiannopoulou, A. Vollas, M. Alatzoglou, P. Oikonomou..... 100
- **The Use and Misuse of Water Quality Indexes in Water Quality Assessment**
I. Benkov, S. Tsakovski..... 101
- **Determination of Trace Elements in Human Urine Samples by ICP-MS**
E. Zafeiraki, E. Vouzaxaki, K. Machera, K.M. Kasiotis..... 102
- **Environmental Assessment of Solid Waste Produced in Greece during the SARS-CoV-2 Pandemic**
K. Bismpa, K. Poulios, A. Zafeirakou, G. Aretoulis..... 103
- **Solid Wastes, Constructions Wastes, Plastic and Microplastics in Agricultural Areas after Flood, the Case of Thessaly**
C. A. Papadimitriou 104
- **Assessment of the Results of Three Surveys Relating to the COVID-19 Pandemic in Greece. Pharmaceuticals, Personal Care/Protection and Cleaning Products Use**
A. Zafeirakou, A. Gkatzioura, K. Kogia, E. Kabioti, B. L. Sismanidis, M. Mpalouris 109

Air Quality and Health

- **War-driven Energy Shifts: Assessing the Impact of Biomass Heating on Milan's Air Quality**
C. Sioutas, Y. Aghaei, M. Mahdi Badami, R. Tohidi..... 113
- **Real-Time Source Apportionment of Fine Atmospheric Aerosols using the AXA (ACSM-Xact-AE33) Set-Up**
M. Manousakas, S. Papagiannis, O. Zografou, M. Gini, S. Vratolis, E. Diapouli, K. Eleftheriadis..... 114
- **Pandemic Preparedness and New Model Developments for Airborne Diseases Transmitting via Aerosols**
A. Alexopoulos..... 116
- **Temporal Variations, Sources and Health Impacts of Particulate Matter in an Industrial Area (Ankara City, Türkiye)**
B. Taşpınar, E. Sağırh, E. Dikmen, Z. Gemici, H. Ertürk, O. Kale, F. Öztürk 126

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Developing a Smart Air Quality Monitoring System: Insights from the Preparatory Phase <i>K.-M. Fameli, A. Kladakis, C. Charalampidou, V.D. Assimakopoulos.....</i> 	127
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● PM₁₀ Mass Concentration and Long-Range Potential Source Contributions at the Eastern Black Sea Atmosphere during the Summer Season <i>S. Gündem, D. D. G. Tokgöz, K.O.Demirarслан, F. Öztürk.....</i> 	128
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Particulate Matter Exposure in Passenger Car Cabin in Athens, Greece <i>K. Ntourou, K-M Fameli, I-A Gkountouva, Ch. Tsitsis, K. Moustris, N. Manousakis.....</i> 	138
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● A Multi-year Record of Precipitation and Ionic Composition at a Remote Site in Eastern Mediterranean: Levels, Sources and Source Regions <i>O. Alsaç, E. Dikmen, E. Sağırılı, İ. Balçılar, A.İ.İlhan, T.Balta, G.Rasan, A.F.Harpur, G.Tuncel, F. Öztürk.....</i> 	146
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Spatially Resolved Chemical Characterization and OP of PM10: an Innovative Approach to Assess Population Exposure to Different PM Sources and Map their Potential Health Impact <i>L. Massimi, C. Perrino, S. Canepari.....</i> 	148
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● A Comparative Forecasting Approach for Fine Particulate Matter (PM_{2.5}) in Istanbul by using Seasonal Grey Model <i>T. Özcan, A. K. Konyalıoğlu.....</i> 	150
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Determination of the Contribution of Natural Sources (primarily Crustal Dust and Sea Salt) to the PM₁₀ Levels in the Mugla province <i>F. Yetgin Baykal, G. Gullu, E. Alp.....</i> 	159
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Mutagenic Activity of Airborne Particulate Matter (PM_{2.5}) in a Dense Residential Area (Bolu City, Türkiye) <i>K.K. Alsaç, M. Aktürk, E. Koçak, N. Demir, S. Aslan, F. Öztürk.....</i> 	160
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Nature-Based Solutions (NbS) for Spatial Mapping of PM Components Released from Fires in urban Settings <i>A. Zara, F. Barisano, C. Tiraboschi, E. Di Martino, S. Canepari, L. Massimi.....</i> 	162
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Model/Experimental Organisms to Estimate oxidative Stress and Health Effects Induced by <i>in vivo</i> Exposure to Different PM Components <i>E. Vaccarella, S. Canepari, V. Lucchesi, F. Cerasti, F. Peruch, V. Mastrantonio, I. Stefani, D. Porretta, L. Massimi.....</i> 	164
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Air Quality and Elemental Concentrations in Hair and Urine of Italian and Chilean University Students <i>R. Giorgione, M.A.L. Guzman, L. Massimi, S. Canepari, M. L. Astolf.....</i> 	166

- **An Integrated Approach of Improving Indoor Air Quality and Energy Saving in Buildings**
T. Maggos, P. Panagopoulos, V. Binas, K. Theodorou, A. Nikolakopoulos, F. Giama, A. Papdopoulos..... 167
- **Source Apportionment of PM₁₀ and its Oxidative Potential by Spatially Resolved Samplings**
C. Tiraboschi, C. Perrino, M. A. Frezzini, E. Vaccarella, A. Amoroso, A. Di Giosa, S. Canepari, L. Massimi..... 168
- **Drivers of PM₁₀ Retention by Black Locust Plantations at Restored Lignite Mines**
Ch.G. Sachanidis,, M.N. Fotelli, N.M. Fyllas, N. Markos, K. Radoglou..... 170
- **Active Monitoring of Heavy Metalair Pollution with Using a Bioindicator ("Sphagnum Bag") in Batumi (South Kholkheti) Georgia**
N. Tetemadze, A. Bakuridze, N. Kiknadze, I. Matchutadze..... 171
- **Optimal Design of an Urban Air-Pollution Monitoring Network**
P. Karakostas, D. Alexiou, A. Sifaleras..... 172

Global Climate Change

- **Neglected Diseases on the Rise: The Clue is in the Name**
P. Karanis..... 181
- **Advancing Resource Recovery and Re-use in the Water-Energy-Food Nexus for a Low-Carbon Economy**
M. Falda, C. Laspidou, G. Adamos, S. Caucci..... 182
- **Integration of Laser Biotechnology and Photovoltaic for Adaptation to Climate Change**
T. Žaba, J. W. Dobrowolski..... 183
- **The Inequity of Global Warming Effects: Reviewing the Socioeconomic Brunt of climate Impacts**
M. Pempetzoglou, P. Tsinaslanidou..... 184
- **Calculation of C in Harvested Woody Products of Deciduous Forest**
V. Dimou, K. Kitikidou, K. Radoglou..... 193
- **An Improved FB-Prophet Model for Wheat Production Forecasting in Turkey**
İ. Bereketli, T. Özcan, A. K. Konyaloğlu..... 202
- **Assessment of Climate Change Impacts on the Central Coastal Collector, Athens Greece**
I. M. Kourtis, I. Aloukos, S. Agiostratitis, I. Karabelas, G. Maltidis, E. Baltas..... 212

Ecotoxicology and Environmental Toxicology

- **Disposable Face Masks into Aquatic Environment: Mediated Aging Process Alterations and Effects on Marine Bivalves**
G. Kalamaras, S. Dailianis..... 215
- **Progress in Ecotoxicity Testing with Duckweeds**
P. Ziegler 216
- **Assessing Tetraglyme-Mediated Effects on Salt- and Freshwater Unicellular Microalgae**
N. Charalambous, G. Grammatikopoulos, S. Dailianis 225
- **Oilseed rape (*Brassica Napus*) Response to Soil Tetracycline and Ciprofloxacin Contamination**
J. Žaltauskaitė, A. Dikšaitytė, G. Kacienė, I. Januškaitienė, D. Miškelytė, G. Sujetovienė, R. Dagiliūtė..... 226
- **Biomarkers: a Useful Tool for Assessing Lake Water Ecological Quality**
D. Petrocheilou, O. Petriki, M. Kaloyianni, D. Bobori..... 227
- **The Ecotoxicological Effects of Tetracycline Compounds and their Mixtures on *Vibrio fischeri*, *Daphnia magna* and *Artemia salina***
L. Balamatsia, C.A. Papadimitriou, A. Moriki, A. Mane, D. Modestou..... 236
- **Effects of Triclosan on Duckweed (*Lemna minor*) and its Recovery Under Elevated Temperature**
D. Miskelyte, J. Zaltauskaite..... 243
- ***Apis mellifera* as a Model Species to Evaluate Toxicological Effects of Fungicides used in Vineyard Agroecosystems**
T. Campani, G. Manieri, I. Caliani, A. Di Noi, L. Giovanetti, S. Casini..... 244
- **Testing and Comparing Three Different Pesticide Leaching Indicators and Recommendations for Future Use**
A. Finizio, A. Tosadori, A. Di Guardo..... 252
- **Honeybees and Hive Products as Bioindicators of Environmental Pollutant**
L. Borriello, M. Scivicco, T. Cirillo, L. Severino, F. Esposito..... 253
- **Experimental Approach for Evaluating the Ability of Hemp (*Cannabis sativa L.*) to Tolerate and Phytoextract Lithium from Environmental Matrices**
G.D'Onofrio, F. Pietrini, L. Passatore, D. Marzi, L. Massimi, M.L. Astolfi, M. Zacchini 254
- **Ecotoxicity Assessment of Graphene Oxide in the Aquatic Ecosystem**
I. Fekete-Kertész, M. Angeli, K. László, B. S. Gyarmati, J. Kutasi, P. Futó, M. Futó, M. Molnár..... 256

- **Environmental Stress on two Freshwater Fish Species**
M. Mitsopoulou, O. Petriki, D. Petrocheilou, M. Kaloyianni and D. Bobori..... 257
- **Fin Deformities in Fish: Effect on Multi-Biomarker Responses and Suitability for Biomonitoring Surveys**
M. Stankevičiūtė, R. Valskienė and J. Dainys 258
- **Cytogenetic Damage in Flounder (*Platichthys flesus*) from the Baltic Sea: Environmental Risk Associated with Oil Terminal in the Lithuanian EEZ**
J. Pažusienė, R. Valskienė, J. Dainys, M. Stankevičiūtė..... 265
- **Environmental Impact of Phthalates on Adult Sea Turtles and Eggs in the Mediterranean Sea**
D. Savoca, S. Orecchio, A. Maccotta 272
- **Effects of Tire Fire Effluents in *Oncorhynchus mykiss*: Exposure and Recovery Study**
G. Sauliūtė, A. Markuckas, Ž. Jurgelėnė, M. Stankevičiūtė..... 274
- **Potential Toxicity of Nine Rare Earth Elements (REEs) on Marine Copepod *Tigriopus fulvus***
F. Biandolino, E. Prato, A. Grattagliano, G. Libralato, M. Trifuoggi, I. Parlapiano 280
- **Multigenerational responses of *Ceriodaphnia dubia* to selected pharmaceuticals and lanthanides**
B. Gylytė, R. Karitonas, V. Martinyuk, V. Baranovskii, K. Yunko, O. Stoliar, L. Manusadžianas..... 290
- **Praseodymium toxicity to representatives of aquatic biota**
R. Karitonas, B. Gylytė, S. Jurkonienė, V. Šveikauskas, V. Baranovskii, K. Yunko, V. O. Stoliar, L. Manusadžianas..... 292

Natural Resources Management

- **Environmental Justice and Perceived Ecosystem Services from Urban Green Infrastructure in two Portuguese Cities**
T. Panagopoulos, M.D.C. Antunes, C.S. Silva 297
- **Natural Regeneration and Restoration of forest Ecosystems after Wildfire in North Evia**
T. Tsitsoni, A. Dimitrakopoulos..... 298
- **Perceptions and Behaviour of National Parks' Visitors: Students' Case from Lithuania**
M. Yatsiuk, D. Miškelytė, R. Dagiliūtė 300

- **Empowering Environmental Conservation by Designing an Information System for Wildlife and Biodiversity Protection Label Award**
M. Spentzou, E. Chatzopoulou, P. Argyraki, A. Giannakopoulos, D.C. Chatzopoulos, A. Economou, C.S. Laspidou, C. Billinis 301
- **Evaluation of Plant Extracts Derived from Aromatic Plants Abundant in the Mediterranean Region as Efficient Phytoprotective Agents**
A. Gropali, I. Stavrakakis, S. Anagnostopoulos, N. Remmas, G. Tsiamis, W. Eisenreich, S. Basiouni, A. Shehata, M. Yilmaz, M. Emekci, F. Acheuk, S. Lasram, G. Sylaios, P. Melidis, S. Ntougias..... 311
- **Hydrological Analysis and Implementation of Combined Nature-Based Solutions in Karditsa Region-Greece**
A.P. Theochari, E. Baltas, J. Jurík, T. Giannakakis 316
- **Interactions between Soil Salinity, Vegetation, and European Hare's (*Lepus europaeus*) Use of Space at Coastal Grazing Lands in Evros Delta, Greece**
I. Karmiris, M. Fotelli, Z. Penios, K. Radoglou..... 325
- **Implementation of Nature-Based Solutions on the Island of Lefkada-Greece**
I. Toumpas, A.P. Theochari, E. Baltas 326
- **Integrated Approach for Environmental Management and Remediation of Contaminated Sites**
G. Felli, P. Ciampi, C. Esposito, L.Mantilacci, M. Petrangeli Papini..... 336
- **Dry-Stone Walls and Terraces: Pillars of Cultural Heritage and Biodiversity – Insights from the Island of Lefkada (Ionian Islands)**
D. Phitos, G. Kamari, P. Bareka, G. Mitsainas, E. Katopodi..... 337
- **Mapping Groundwater Dependent Ecosystems for Sustainable Management of Aquifers**
G. Kolitsi, D. Charchousi, N. K. Mellios, M. P. Papadopoulou..... 338

NexusNet-COST Action Network on Water-Energy-Food Nexus

- **A System Dynamics Model to Assess the Water-Energy-Food-Ecosystems Nexus at Transboundary River Basin Level**
N. Mellios, I. Kourtis, M.P. Papadopoulou, V.A. Tsihrintzis, C. Laspidou..... 349
- **Advancing Organizational Aspects of WEF Nexus Policy Implementation: A Particular Need for Developing Countries**
S. Živković, T. Radjenović, D. Vasović, Ž. Vranjanac, Ž. Radjenović 350
- **WEF Nexus Sustainability Indicators at Urban Scale: a Systematic Review**
B. Feizollahbeigi, L.P. Dias, J. Seixas 351

- **Comparative Analysis of WEF Index in Western Balkan Countries and EU Developed Countries: WEF Indicators Applicability to Public Utilities**
Ž. Vranjanac, Ž. Radjenović, D. Vasović, S. Živković, T. Radjenović 352
- **Assessment and Mitigation of Uncertainty in Modelling Regional Resilience against Climate Change**
D. Kofinas, M. Drews, R. Ludwig, C. Moujan, I. La Jeunesse, G. Papangelis, K. Ziliaskopoulos, E. Athanasopoulou, N. Votsi, N. Cruz Perez, Juan C. Santamarta, G. Adamos, D. Kassiteropoulou, S. Mimis, C. Laspidou..... 353
- **Exploring the Water, Energy, Food, Transport and Health Nexus Approach to Enhance Biodiversity Resilience under Climate Change—the Pilot Case Study of Greece**
A. E. Ioannou, D. Kasiteropoulou, K. Ziliaskopoulos, C. S. Laspidou 355
- **The Integration of NbSs in NDCs: towards an Evidence-based Assessment Framework at the EU Level**
G. Tseva, A. Spyropoulou, A. Vion Loisel and C. Laspidou 519

Advances in Water and Wastewater Treatment

- **Graphene Oxide Derivatives Doped with Chitosan/Activated Carbon for the Removal of Heavy Metals from Wastewaters**
K. N. Maroulas, A. K. Tolkou, P. Efthymiopoulos, I. K. Konstantinou, S. Ntougias, I. A. Katsoyiannis, G. Z. Kyzas..... 359
- **Bio-Graphene Nanocomposite Polymeric Membranes for the Mitigation of Biofouling**
C. Alatzoglou, M. Patila, M.G. Trachioti, A.C. Polydera, M. I. Prodromidis, H. Stamatis..... 361
- **Valve Isolation Placement to Mitigate Contaminant Spreading in Water Distribution Network**
G.F. Santonastaso, A. Di Nardo, R. Greco..... 363
- **Evaluation of Struvite Precipitation in Anaerobic Hybrid Systems with the PHREEQC Program**
I. Y. Guney, S. Hasanoglu, G. Yilmaz, Y. Kaya, I. Vergili, C. Aydiner, Z. B. Gönder..... 364
- **Bio-Catalytic Removal of Pharmaceutically Active Compounds from Water using Peroxidase Immobilized onto Modified Fe₃O₄ Biochar Composite**
M. Petronijević, S. Panić, I. Antić, J. Živančev, D. Rakić, N. Đurišić-Mladenović..... 365
- **A Topological Backtracking Methodology for Sensor Location in Sewer Systems**
A. Simone, C. Di Cristo, V. Guadagno, G. Del Giudice..... 367

- **Determination of ILI - Infrastructure Leakage Index Using the Analyses of Minimum Night Flows**
L. Tuhovčák, M. Poláchová..... 368
- **Organic Loading Rate, Ammonia and Salt Effects on Microbial Shift in Anaerobic Systems**
S. Hasanoglu, I. Y. Guney,, I. Vergili, G. Yilmaz, Y. Kaya, C. Aydinler, Z. B. Gönder..... 369
- **Synergistically Enhanced Removal of Phenolic Effluents with Fabricated Sulfur Doped Carbon Modified Trimetallic Catalyst**
I. Aslam, A. T. A. Kainat, M. N. Zafar..... 370
- **Operation of an Anaerobic Expanded Granular Sludge Bed (EGSB) MBR System Treating Domestic Wastewater**
E. Politou, K. Azis, A. Makri, S. Ntougias, P. Melidis..... 371
- **Algicidal Strain of *Bacillus velezensis* IMV B-7571 for Controlling Harmful Algal Blooms**
N. Rybalchenko, M. Kharkhota, L. Avdeeva, O. Lyanzberh, N. Matviienko..... 372
- **Graphene Oxide Nanoparticles for Water Purification in the Post-War Period: Removal of Heavy Metals from Water Bodies**
Ž. Jurgelėnė, S. Šemčuk, N. Kazlauskienė, S. N. Matviienko, Skrotskyi, R. Butrimienė, M. Kazlauskas, D. Montvydienė..... 373
- **Eco-Friendly Nano-Adsorbents for Removal of Emerging Contaminants in Aquatic Ecosystems**
S. Šemčuk, D. Montvydienė, N. Kazlauskienė, V. Pakštas, V. Bukauskas, M. Javed, G. Lujanienė, K. Jokšas, Ž. Jurgelėnė..... 380
- **Suspended Solids Removal from Municipal Wastewater by the Use of a Hydrocyclone**
K. Tsamoutsoglou, A. Kechagias, P. Gikas..... 381

Industrial Symbiosis and Sustainable Production

- **Column Experiments Utilizing Iron Nanocomposite Material for the Removal of Heavy Metal Mixture**
C. Mystrioti, N. Papassiopi, A. Xenidis..... 385
- **Use of Nano-Biocatalysts for the Conversion of CO₂ to Formic Acid**
C. Gakis, A. Karaiskou, R. Fotiadou, M. Patila, K. Spyrou, A. C. Polydera, D. Gournis, H. Stamatis..... 386
- **Investigating the Potential of Gaseous Biofuels Production from Sugary and Starchy Biowastes**
M. Alexandropoulou, T. Kalogirou, M. Hashem, I. Ntaikou..... 387

- **Comparison of Polyhydroxyalkanoates Production Efficiency from Acidified Kitchen Biowastes in sequential Batch and Fed Batch Mode**
I. Kranias, E. Kora, I. Ntaikou, G. Lyberatos 388
- **Milk Thistle Cultivation as a Heavy Metal Accumulator of Polluted Soils and its Impact on the Circular Economy**
S. G.Papadimou, E. E.Golia..... 389
- **Biotransformation of Agri-Food Wastes to Produce Health-Promoting Bioactive Compounds**
J. Squillante, I. Romano, F. Esposito, S. Velotto, O. Pepe, T. Cirillo..... 390
- **Evaluating Circular Economy Practices: a Questionnaire-Based Approach**
E. R. Pachon, R. Canavesi, M. Sorlini 391
- **3D-Printed Graphene Biosensor Arrays for the Detection of ALP and RUNX2 Osteogenic Biomarkers**
M. Ionita, A. E. Chiticaru 392
- **Sustainability of 3d Printed Bridges**
P. Boutsikas, A. Chortis, A. Iliadi-Manou, K. Katakalos 393
- **Harnessing Waste Reuse: Lipase Immobilization on Lignocellulosic Wastes for Sustainable Biocatalysis and Circular Economy Enhancement**
V. Chiappini, C. Conti, M. L. Astolfi, A. M. Girelli 394
- **Sustainability of Prefabricated Concrete Foundation of a Smart Car Park (Green City Parking)**
A. Chortis, A. Iliadi-Manou, H. Spanos, K. Katakalos..... 396
- **Conversion of Microwave/Ultrasound Pretreated Birch Sawdust into Platform Chemicals in Aqueous Deep Eutectic Solvent**
S. Kälkäjä, J-M. Lévêque, K. Lappalainen 397
- **The Challenge of Ammonia Free Soil Bio-Cementation and Recent Breakthroughs: A Review of Phosphate Minerals for Soil Biocementation**
S. Joshi, M. Mavroulidou, M.J. Gunn 398
- **Application of CO₂ - Induced Carbonate Minerals for Soil Treatment**
H. A. Keykha, M. Mavroulidou, H. Mohamadzadeh Romiani..... 408
- **Biological Activity of Lactic Acid Bacteria Isolated from Sterlet (*Acipenser ruthenus*) and Atlantic Sturgeon (*Acipenser oxyrinchus*)**
O. Vasyliuk, S. Skrotskyi, L. Khomenko..... 415
- **Table Olive Processing Wastewater Management: Current Situation and Future Perspectives**
Ch. Siavala, D. Bobori, A. Kapagiannidis..... 417

- **Adopting the ISO 14001 Environmental Management System in the Water Treatment Plant of Thessaloniki, Greece**
K. Kalaitzidou, C. Albanakis, Seretoudi G..... 418
- **A Novel Leaching Approach for the Treatment of LARCO Ferronickel Plant Dust Samples**
S. Tampouris, T. Abo Atia, K. Binnemans 425
- **The Implementation Of Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) to the Iron and Steel Industry**
S. Koutroumpelis, A. Kungolos..... 430
- **Physicochemical and Ecotoxicological Evaluation of Municipal Biosolids for Agricultural Use**
I. Giannakis, A. Terzidis, P. Ntailiani, C. Emmanouil, A. Kungolos 432
- **Business Sectors Affected by Transition towards Circular Economy: A Literature Review**
C. Kalantzis, K. Aravossis..... 433

Environmental Education

- **Citizen Science Approach to Create a Biodiversity Observatory through the MINKA Platform for the Athens Metropolitan Area**
A. E. Ioannou, E. Hatzieleftheriou, K. Ntai, C. S. Laspidou..... 437
- **Building Participative Scenarios on Coastal Areas: what Knowledge/Education do we Need?**
A. L’Astorina, A. De Lazzari, A. Pugnetti..... 438
- **Prevention and Protection of Health and the Environment in Laboratories Using Advanced and Innovative Biotechnological Methods: Results of an Italian Project**
E. Sturchio, M. Zanellato, P. Boccia..... 439
- **Crossing Language Boundaries in Environmental Engineering: Study on Terminology Translation and Adoption of a Contrastive Analysis Elaboration Tool of Seven Variables in Academic Textbooks Highlighting Intercultural Differences**
S. Christidou..... 450
- **Experiencing Biodiversity Using Members of the Genus *Tulipa* as a Model: A Novel Approach for High School Students with a Karyotype Study Lab Experiment**
E. Kriemadi, N. Krigas, P. Bareka..... 462

- **A Review on The Application of Gamification and Serious Games in Environmental Education**
C. A. Papadimitriou, I. Papoutsis, S. Galinou-Mitsoudi, I. Deliyannis..... 463
- **Circular Waste Management towards a Green Agreement (Zero Waste to Landfill), in Relation to the Certification and the Sustainable Early Preschool Education (a Toolkit for Accelerating UN- SDGs)**
V. Tryfona, C. Panagopoulou, E. Panagopoulou, A.Kungolos 468

Environmental Economics

- **Incentivizing Sustainable Agriculture: Assessing Economic Values and Farmer Willingness-to-Accept in Carbon Farming**
D. Latinopoulos, K. Bithas, D. Triantakostas..... 473
- **The Correlation between Internal and External Customer's Satisfaction as Basis to Improve Organizational Management**
I. Gertner MorYossef..... 482
- **EU27's Optimal Environmental Economics Solution Assessment Utilizing Various Weighting Techniques for MCDM Procedures**
Ž.Rađenović, Ž.Vranjanac 483
- **Social Cost Benefit Analysis on the Implementation of Forest Projects in the Mediterranean**
M. Christantonil, P. Vourna, G. Davettas, AM. Giarenti, S. Mardiri, D. Moscholiou Syrigou, C. Stamati, G. Tentes, P. Batziaki..... 484
- **A Multicriteria Model for Rational Water Management through the New Common Agricultural Policy rules**
A. Kouriati, C. Moulogianni, E. Lialia, A.Tafidou, A. Prentzas, E. Dimitriadou, T. Bournaris 493

Environmental Legislation and Policies

- **A Mini Review of Sewage Sludge Treatment and Management in Greece: Recent History, Development and Future Challenges**
A. Eleftheriadou, C.S. Akratos, A. Vavatsikos, M. Gratziou..... 497
- **Legal Issues Arising from the Caisson Breach during Port Construction in Piraeus, Greece**
K. Mavrilakos, D. Vini, B.S. Tselentis..... 509

- **The Implementation of the Maritime Spatial Planning Directive in Greece:
An Opportunity to Promote Equity and Social Justice by Balancing
National Strategic Goals with Local Interests**
V. Vassilopoulou..... 510
- **An Overview of the Turkish Regulations on NRW Reduction**
A. Muhammetoglu, T. Akdeniz, P. Orhan, M. Sapiano, H. Muhammetoglu..... 511

- Author Index**..... 521
- Subject Index**..... 531
- Sponsors**..... 543

Bio-Catalytic Removal of Pharmaceutically Active Compounds from Water using Peroxidase Immobilized onto Modified Fe₃O₄-Biochar Composite

**M. Petronijević*, S. Panić, I. Antić, J. Živančev, D. Rakić
and N. Đurišić-Mladenović**

University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Technology Novi Sad, 21000 Novi Sad, Serbia

** Corresponding author: E-mail: mirjana.petronijevic@uns.ac.rs,
Tel +381214853633, Fax: +38121450413*

Abstract

Pharmaceutically active compounds (PhACs) such as antibiotics and analgesics are organic substances that can be found in natural water resources. Most of these compounds reach natural waters through the discharge of wastewater. Many of these compounds persist in wastewater because conventional water treatment processes are not designed to remove them. Failure to remove PhACs in municipal wastewater facilities leads to contamination of water resources, which evolves into serious environmental and human health problems, including antibiotic resistance spread. Therefore, there is a need to find innovative approaches for removing these pollutants from water.

One of these processes is the biocatalytic removal of pharmaceuticals from water using immobilized enzymes such as peroxidases. Peroxidases are known for their ability to degrade different organic pollutants, resulting in their efficient removal from water. The advantage of bio-catalytic processes lies in their selectivity and relative specificity towards certain substances. It is also important to reduce the formation of toxic by-products, so to enable more precise treatment of polluted water.

This work aims to investigate the efficiency of selected PhACs removal from water using horseradish peroxidase immobilized onto Fe₃O₄-biochar composite. The Fe₃O₄-biochar composite was synthesized in laboratory conditions by co-precipitation and used as enzyme solid support. The enzyme was covalently bonded onto support across glutaraldehyde and used as a bio-catalyst in the water treatment process. The mixture of 9 PhACs (in the concentration of 10 µg/L of each compound) in deionized water was used as a model water sample with environmentally relevant contaminants levels. The removal of PhACs was performed using immobilized peroxidase in the presence of hydrogen peroxide at neutral pH conditions for 1 hour.

To determine the adsorption properties of the Fe₃O₄-biochar composite, the process was carried out without hydrogen peroxide in the first 20 minutes, while the biocatalytic reaction was enhanced by the addition of hydrogen peroxide. The removal of PhACs from water by adsorption was 5-92%, where removal rates above 50% were recorded for salbutamol, ofloxacin, sotalol, atenolol, diltiazem, and clarithromycin.

By applying the bio-catalytic process, significantly better results are achieved in terms of the removal of all tested compounds (70-100%) compared to adsorption. For a third of the total number of the investigated compounds (acetaminophen, salbutamol, and clarithromycin)

complete removal was achieved after 5 min of the catalytic process. It can be concluded that the immobilized peroxidase shows a high application potential in the removal of pharmaceuticals from water.

Keywords: *pharmaceuticals removal, peroxidase, Fe₃O₄- biochar composite, bio-catalytic process*

Acknowledgments:

This research was funded by the European Union. However, the views and opinions expressed are those of the authors only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or EU executive agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible. This study was conducted under the TwiNSol-CECs project, which received funding from a Horizon Europe program under grant agreement No. 101059867.